

ARTICLE 1. EVIDENCE ACADEMY (EA) INSTRUCTIONAL GUIDE

THE PURPOSE OF THE EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY INSTRUCTIONAL GUIDE IS TO DOCUMENT THE PROCESSES OF PLANNING A VIRTUAL EVIDENCE ACADEMY (EA) EVENT. THE GUIDE MAY BE USED AS A RESOURCE FOR EA STAFF MEMBERS TO REFERENCE THROUGHOUT THE PLANNING PROCESS OF EA EVENTS. IT MAY ALSO ASSIST OTHER PROGRAM TEAMS TO PLAN VIRTUAL ENGAGED CONFERENCES AROUND OTHER HEALTH AND HEALTH EQUITY RELATED TOPICS.

(A) BACKGROUND

The Evidence Academy (EA) is an engaged conference model developed by North Carolina Translational and Clinical Sciences (NC TraCS) Institute at UNC-Chapel Hill. It is a widely used and innovative approach that has been applied to a variety of health topics to facilitate the translation of knowledge and evidence into practice and policy (Rohweder, 2016). EA conferences typically center around a theme and leverage community engagement methods and health equity principles to convene diverse stakeholders (e.g., researchers, health professionals, and policy makers) **to co-learn through keynote and breakout presentations and to collaboratively action plan through discussions and consensus building**. The EA model is composed of the following key elements: 1) a Data Profile, or document which thematically summarizes current data and evidence related to the event’s primary topic and is distributed to attendees prior to the event, grounding them in a common knowledge of the topic to be discussed; 2) a 1-2 day in-person or virtual convening that generates knowledge sharing and action planning; and 3) the dissemination of key takeaways and lessons learned via an EA Summary Report and community-tailored dissemination strategy. This model has been implemented regionally in in-person settings, as well as nationally via a virtual platform, and allows planners the flexibility to adapt event settings, agendas, and objectives to their program’s need.

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostic Testing – Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Initiative, funded by the NIH, partnered with NC TraCS to adapt the EA model to an annual, national, virtual event that convened RADx-UP research teams and community partners. The annual RADx-UP event series is titled the “RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy”, and the events’ themes center around COVID-19 testing equity and its associated factors. This instructional guide documents the processes adapted and created by the EA internal operating team beginning in Fall of 2020.

(B) PARTIES RESPONSIBLE FOR EA PROGRAM ACTIVITIES

Planning of EA events involves three core groups of stakeholders. Each has a specific scope of responsibility. See table below.

Table 1: Evidence Academy Program Planning Teams

Team	Scope of Responsibility	Members
EA Internal Operations Team (IOT)	To plan, coordinate, and implement the projects and deliverables associated with the EA Program. Meet on a weekly or biweekly basis.	EA Program Coordinator, 2 EA Assistant Program Coordinators, Operational Lead, RADx-UP Project Liaison
EA Planning Team	To provide insight and feedback on the major deliverables associated with the EA program. Meet on a quarterly basis.	Staff and faculty associated with RADx-UP, with a focus on sharing expertise from various workstreams and outside work that would inform themes and speakers for EA. The number of members varies based on many factors (i.e. conference size, organization size, etc.)
EA Steering Committee (SC)	To share expertise and guidance on the selection of event themes, content, and speakers. Meet three times per event cycle.	Diverse group of community partner and academic representatives from across the USA and territories with proven expertise in areas related to event themes. 12 – 15 members.

(C) EA PROGRAM CYCLE

The EA model includes deliverables that precede and proceed the EA event itself and are conducted on an annual basis. The key deliverables of each event cycle are the EA Data Profile, the EA event and agenda (see Appendix Item D for template of agenda), the EA Summary Report, and a Community Dissemination Resource.

Figure 1 and Table 2 demonstrate the sequential order of the program cycle and descriptions of the deliverables and their activities.

Figure 1: Descriptions of Key Activities and Deliverables

EA Program Activity	Description
Identify Topic and Perform Literature Review	Identify the core event topic then review SARS-CoV literature through an equity lens to identify prominent themes.
Development of EA Themes	Thematically summarize literature to inform Data Profile and EA event agenda.
Create and Distribute Data Profile	Publish and disseminate a Data Profile prior to EA event. Profile centers participants around the state of the science and themes to be discussed at EA, relying on community input for translation of content.
Convene Evidence Academy	Convene the conference (“day of show”) for 3-4 hours each day over a 2-day period, to share and collectively understand the state-of-the science, or the current evidence of COVID-19 testing and related factors in the populations most impacted.
Create and Distribute Summary Report	Develop and disseminate an event Summary Report which synthesizes content, key takeaways, lessons learned.
Create and Distribute Community Member Resources	Develop accessible resources for disseminating EA learnings and outcomes to RADx-UP community partners.
Incorporate Lessons Learned	Use participants’ feedback to plan the next EA Program cycle.

Table 2: Evidence Academy Program Annual Event Cycle

ARTICLE 2. EA EVENT PLANNING PROCESS

SECTION 2.01 DEVELOPING AND DISSEMINATING EVENT REGISTRATION AND INVITATIONS

(A) DEFINING THE TARGET AUDIENCE

Define the target audience of the event by consulting with the project's Principal Investigator(s) to understand expectations for the event. The final evaluation goals and outcomes should reflect the intended audience also. Secondary audience members should be invited to the EA event at the request of other project members (e.g., RADx-UP MPIs, NIH leadership, operational leadership, and any other external stakeholders).

(B) BUILDING EVENT INVITATION LISTS

Because EA events are invitation only and there are limited seats based on budget restrictions, a nomination process is suggested so that teams may determine which members should attend. Additionally, the process allows EA staff to emphasize to project teams that community organization partners must be included in the nomination. The nomination process is optional and can be bypassed if leadership and the IOT are not concerned with certain metrics like number of attendees. Nominations will be collected by:

- Creating a nomination form that captures all the data you will need to send nominees the official registration invitation (first name, last name, institution/community-based organization, etc.)
- Drafting a clear message for project leadership inviting them to nominate members of their team. Include a set of instructions that includes the number of participants they may nominate and how to use the form
- Sharing the nomination process and form via program wide mailing lists, during project wide meetings, or through program staff tasked with managing the projects

(C) DISSEMINATING REGISTRATION INVITATIONS

After the nomination process has closed or after a date has been set to open registration, all nominated individuals should receive an email invitation to register for the event. It should include clear instructions for how to complete an included registration form and a message about what registered attendees can expect to receive in the weeks leading up to the event.

- **Registration form:** Develop questions based on the event’s evaluation goals and objectives and logistical needs for the program. Registration should include collection of demographics, attendee type (CDCC staff, academic partner, community partner, NIH, other, etc.) and selection of preferred breakout sessions.
- **Confirmation email:** Create an email message to be sent automatically to attendees once registration is complete to confirm their form has been received and to provide additional instructions on logging into the event. Consider including any additional details that attendees should know about such as other communications they can anticipate receiving and provide a calendar invitation to hold the time on attendees’ calendar.
- **Monitoring Registration:** Monitor the registration list closely leading up to the event and be prepared to send additional invitations upon request by leadership or if nominations are submitted after the deadline. Create reminder email messages to be sent to those who were nominated but have not completed registration and send them out periodically leading up to the day of the event. Assign a team member to field ad hoc requests and send out individual email invitations to approved individuals.

SECTION 2.02 COORDINATION OF THE EA STEERING COMMITTEE

THE PURPOSE OF THE EVIDENCE ACADEMY STEERING COMMITTEE (SC) IS TO ENGAGE TOPIC EXPERTS IN THE ENVISIONING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EVENT CONTENT.

(A) DEVELOPING EA SC DOCUMENTATION

Before initiating the process of SC member selection, the internal operations team should develop the following documents:

- **EA Program SC Charter:** Defines the overall purpose of the SC, which should be broad enough to use throughout multiple event cycles. The charter should establish the SC’s purpose, goals, structure, and membership terms and processes. This document may be revised at the beginning of each event cycle to reflect programmatic changes and any identified areas for process improvement.
- **SC Scope of Work:** Defines the specific scope of work that SC members will be asked to perform during the given event cycle. It should include the event’s goals, overall theme, tentative SC work timeline, and purpose of each of the three SC meetings that will be held leading up to the event.

(B) SC MEMBERSHIP RECRUITMENT AND ONBOARDING

The IOT should consult with program leadership and colleagues to identify potential new SC members as needed depending on the defined terms. New SC candidates should be topic experts related to the overall theme of the current event cycle, and they should be able to provide recommendations for speakers related to the theme and provide feedback on event content which will ultimately shape the EA agenda and Data Profile. The internal team will engage current and new members following the processes outlined below.

- **Engaging Current SC Members:** Draft an email message to be sent to the previous event cycle's SC members who are still eligible to participate based on the defined SC member terms. They should be sent updated versions of the EA SC Charter and EA SC Scope of Work, key dates, honorarium offered, and a deadline to decline if they cannot participate. SC members who are no longer eligible to participate should receive a thank you message, be provided general updates about the next event, and should be invited to attend.
- **Inviting New SC Members:** IOT should draft an email invitation to be sent to all new SC candidates and prepare the EA Program SC Charter and SC Scope of Work documents to be attached to the invitation. The invitation should provide key details of the ask for potential SC members including key dates, time commitment, honorarium offered, and deadline for commitment.
 - **New SC Member Onboarding:** Each new SC member will need to fill out an onboarding form and all (new and current) members will need to provide necessary paperwork to receive their honorarium. The digital onboarding form will collect relevant information. Current members should be asked to review the form and provide any updates to information that was previously collected for the last event cycle. Items to be collected include:
 1. Member's first and last name
 2. Member's professional title
 3. Contact information
 4. Support staff name and contact information
 5. A brief bio, no more than 250 words
 6. A headshot

(C) SC MANAGEMENT

Disseminating a SC ‘Welcome Packet’: SC members should be provided a digital ‘welcome packet’ of resources and documents related to the work, which should be provided in an email at least two weeks prior to the first SC meeting to allow time for review and preparation. The packet may include:

- SC Meeting 1 Agenda
- EA Skeletal Agenda and tentative event themes
- EA SC Scope of Work
- EA SC Program Charter
- SC Member Profiles (using the digital onboarding form data, this document provides background information on each member and will be used to provide SC profiles on the event platform)

SC Meetings Agenda Overview and Preparation

- *SC Meeting 1:* Members will receive an overview of the EA program, review the proposed themes, be presented with instructions for nominating event speakers, and review the Advancing Community-Academic Partnerships Presentation Series call for presentations. The IOT should send an email immediately following the meeting with:
 - A poll to determine combined availability for meetings 2 and 3;
 - A review of the speaker nomination instructions and links to a digital nomination form.
- *SC Meeting 2:* A member of the IOT will facilitate discussions around the nominated speakers, refining the event themes and addressing any concerns regarding content. The IOT may ask individual SC members for assistance with:
 - Outreach to speakers nominated who have not been responsive to invitations to speak;
 - Reviewing ACAP applications;
 - Finalizing their honorarium paperwork.
- *SC Meeting 3:* The IOT and SC will review the final EA agenda, finalize ACAP presentation teams, and discuss any outstanding content consultation needs. The meeting facilitator should also ensure all SC members have received invites to register for the event and answer any outstanding questions.

SECTION 2.03 EA DATA PROFILE DEVELOPMENT AND DISSEMINATION

THE PURPOSE OF THE EA DATA PROFILE IS TO GROUND ATTENDEES IN THE CURRENT EVIDENCE AROUND COVID-19 TESTING EQUITY AND ITS RELATED FACTORS PRIOR TO THE

EVENT SO THAT A COMMON UNDERSTANDING OF THE EVENTS' THEMES IS ESTABLISHED. THIS SUPPORTS ATTENDEES' ABILITY TO MEANINGFULLY ENGAGE WITH THE SESSIONS' CONTENT AND IN GROUP DISCUSSIONS.

(A) DATA PROFILE AND EVENT THEME DEVELOPMENT

- **Selecting the EA Event's Themes:** EA leadership members generate a broad event theme based on the current cultural climate and relevant challenges or advancements in COVID-19 testing and vaccination equity that have been expressed by project participants, through discussions with RADx-UP's principal investigators, and relevant current events. Once a broad theme has been determined, the IOT will conduct a literature review of the current evidence. Themes that emerge from the literature review are refined through discussion with leadership and further exploration until several event themes have been established.
- **Thematic Summaries Developments:** Findings from the literature review are compiled and drafted into a lay friendly summary. Readers should be able to read the thematic summaries and get a general understanding of the current evidence in the literature around the theme and how it impacts COVID-19 testing and vaccination equity.

(B) IN-CONTEXT INTERVIEWS

Project team members, community partners and academic institution representatives are interviewed by EA leadership using an interview guide that prompts responses from the interviewees about the theme's relationship to their project work. The interviews are woven throughout the data profile to provide further context to how the theme is related to the RADx-UP enterprise and to provide examples of promising practices in conducting community-engaged research from both the community partners' and the academic institutes' perspectives.

- **Selecting Interview Candidates:** The IOT will review the list of current RADx-UP projects and their project descriptions to identify teams that are likely able to speak to the connection of their work to the themes. Diversity of geography, roles, communities served, and project settings will also be considered when determining the best fits for the interviews.
- **Outreach and Scheduling of Interviews:** The RADx-UP Project Liaison will work closely with the EA coordinators to conduct outreach and schedule interviews with project team members. The project liaison works directly with projects and other staff who also serve as lead contacts between projects and RADx-UP CDCC. The individual in this role can use these relationships to make introductions and

determine the best way to reach out to individual project team members. Once an individual agrees to be interviewed, the coordinators will work with EA leadership to schedule a 45-minute Zoom interview.

- **Preparing Interview Content for Publication:** Interviews are conducted and recorded using Zoom, and once interviews are complete the IOT should collect the interviewees' bio and headshot to be included in the data profile. Interviews will be roughly transcribed to find impactful quotes and messages shared in the interview, which will be highlighted throughout the data profile. Links to the recorded interviews are embedded in the Data Profile alongside the key quotes.

(C) DESIGN AND PRODUCTION

The EA team, along with the support of a graphic design team, works to organize and present the Data Profile. The Data Profile is made available in both English and Spanish. 508 Compliant PDF formats are made available for ease of access. The typical formatting of the Data Profile includes the following sections:

- **What This Data Profile Includes:** Outlines the layout of the Data Profile as well as how to use the interactive website.
- **Executive Summary:** Details the purpose of the Data Profile from the perspective of EA leadership.
- **Evidence Academy Contributors:** Covers basic information about the EA speakers and contributors.
- **RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Themes 1-6:** Thematic summaries give general information about the themes developed for the Equity Evidence Academy as well as how those themes relate to the work being done by RADx-UP.
- **About RADx-UP:** Gives relevant context to better understand the RADx-UP initiative.
- **Glossary of Terms:** Defines and provides context for any words or phrases that may be unfamiliar to a layperson.
- **Acknowledgements:** Recognizes all those who have made contributions in the development of the Data Profile.

(D) DISSEMINATION AND EVALUATION

The EA team partners with a team of evaluation experts on the development and implementation of basic survey questions to determine if the Data Profile meets the needs of readers. The survey is programmed using Typeform or a similar service and is embedded directly in the Data Profile interactive webpage. Evaluation questions may include:

1. What is your role in RADx-UP?

- A. Project Team Member-academic institution
 - B. Project Team Member-community partner
 - C. CDCC Staff Member
 - D. Other
2. How likely are you to use the information from this report?
- A. Not at all likely
 - B. Somewhat likely
 - C. Quite likely
 - D. Very likely
3. Please rate the overall quality of the Data Profile:
- A. Very poor
 - B. Poor
 - C. Good
 - D. Very good

**Those who answer "Good" or "Very good" for Q3 are directed to short-answer Q4:*

4. What did you like most about the Data Profile?

**Those who answer "Poor" or "Very poor" for Q3 are directed to short-answer Q5:*

5. What could be improved about the Data Profile?

(For example, the content, the layout, the video interviews, etc.)

SECTION 2.04 VIRTUAL EVENT PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT

(A) FIRST TIME VENDOR SELECTION AND ONBOARDING PROCESS

If a virtual event platform vendor is needed, the IOT team will interview potential vendors and select one that offers required capabilities to support the agenda structure of EA events. Once the vendors' status with the university has been established, EA staff members will

need to submit the following documents to get a signature from the institution's contract department and establish payment processes.

- **Vendor Onboarding Documents:**
 - Vendor's W-9
 - HB Brand Vendor Specific Waiver of Competition
 - Sole Source Justification
 - Vendor Contract Agreement

(B) VENDOR CAPABILITIES NEEDED TO SUPPORT EA'S AGENDA STRUCTURE

- **Registration support:** The platform should support mass communications with registered attendees so that the IOT can easily send out updates and relevant post-event messages efficiently. The registration should also have a mechanism available to group attendees into breakout and roundtable rooms based on their preference selected at registration.
- **Agenda Support:**
 - Ability to have up to 500 virtual participants in the same conference space at once for keynotes and main conference sessions
 - Ability to host up to six concurrent breakout sessions
 - Ability to provide small roundtable discussions of no more than 20 participants simultaneously
 - Ability to provide informal networking spaces for no more than 10 participants simultaneously
- **Networking Capabilities:** Ideally, the platform should include networking features that allow participants to connect meaningfully outside of the formal EA event sessions. These features may include one-on-one meetings and chat abilities and the ability to pair conference participants in informal networking sessions by 'type'.
- **Accessibility and Inclusion:** The platform should provide options for closed captioning and translation during the EA event. During the registration process registrants can indicate any accommodation needs, which the staff will review and communicate with the individual(s) how to access translation or other accommodations as needed.
- **Speaker Onboarding and Training Support:** Vendor should make themselves available in advance of the event to train event speakers to log into the platform, advance slides, use the microphone and camera, and engage with audience as needed/desired.

- **Volunteer Onboarding and Training:** Vendor should make themselves available for group trainings for event staff volunteers in advance of the meeting. Training should include any features that will be utilized by staff members per their role. For more information on Volunteers see section 'Volunteers'.
- **Internal Staff Communication:** The platform should provide a 'room' where internal staff members can meet throughout the conference to troubleshoot and resolve any issues as needed.
- **Day of Event Technical Support:** Vendor should make themselves available during the event to offer Speakers and Volunteers support with accessing sessions, sharing and advancing slides, accessing microphone and camera settings, and other platform related issues.

(C) MEETING WITH PLATFORM VENDORS

- **Ongoing Communications:** IOT staff should meet with vendor representatives periodically to build the platform, plan registration and communications timelines, and receive training on the platform for any features that staff may need to use leading up to, during, and after the event.
- **Run of Show Rehearsal:** Prior to the event all relevant stakeholders should attend a rehearsal where the platform vendor walks through each step of the run of show/production schedule to ensure that all slide decks are correctly timed, flow from one session to the next is seamless, etc.

SECTION 2.05 PLANNING AND EXECUTING THE EA RUN OF SHOW

THE PURPOSE OF A RUN OF SHOW (ROS) DOCUMENT IS TO RECORD THE DETAILED ACTIONS OR INSTRUCTIONS TO BE TAKEN BY THE IOT MEMBERS, EVENT VOLUNTEERS, AND THE PLATFORM VENDOR'S TEAM MEMBERS DURING THE EVENT.

- **ROS Development Process:** The ROS is a living, iterative document that IOT members can begin populating early in the planning process, and it provides a visual for team members to refer to when planning event details and logistics. The final ROS document should be shared across all members of the IOT, platform teams, and possibly the event volunteers. Any last-minute changes to the ROS must be shared across all parties to ensure that production of the event runs smoothly.
- **ROS Format:** Using the EA event's agenda, a ROS document should be drafted early in event planning and updated and refined throughout the planning process. Each event session should be included in the ROS and minute by minute timing should detail when and who

will perform actions including inputting chat scripts, providing prompts to complete session evaluations, and sharing session slide decks.

- **ROS 'Roles'**: Prior to the EA event, the IOT should determine what roles are needed to support the event agenda and assign roles to team members. Roles that are needed on the day of the event have included:
 - **Volunteer Manager**: Closely monitor the volunteers' group chat to answer questions and assist as needed.
 - **Registration Manager**: This individual should be listed as the contact person for those who attempt to register on the day of the event, and they should be prepared to quickly provide event access on a case-by-case basis.
 - **Chat Script Manager**: This individual is responsible for placing messages into the chat at appropriate times as outlined by the ROS and to monitor the attendees' comments and questions during main conference sessions that are made in the chat.

SECTION 2.06 EVIDENCE ACADEMY EVALUATION PROCESSES

Evaluation of the EA event and the program's deliverables is designed and analyzed by the IOT in partnership with an evaluation team that conducts evaluation for the RADx-UP initiative. The two teams work together to determine the events' evaluation goals and methods of data collection, which may vary between program cycles. By design, there are multiple opportunities during the event to collect data from participants regarding individual event sessions, and at the close of an EA an overall survey that comprehensively evaluates the event is disseminated to all attendees. Gift card raffles for participation have yielded higher response rates and should be offered when possible.

Once all evaluation activities are complete the evaluation team compiles results into a slide deck and provides slides that summarize key findings and recommendations. The slides are shared with the IOT and leadership, and they may be used to develop presentations for other RADx-UP meetings as requested. The findings and recommendations are used to inform future planning efforts.

(A) DEMOGRAPHIC DATA COLLECTION

A key component of the EA model is to have a diverse attendee profile so that multiple perspectives are brought to the table for co-learning and generation of recommendations or lessons learned in the roundtable discussions. Demographic data is collected at registration to determine the diversity of attendees and presented to the audience during the opening EA session on Day 1.

- Demographic Data points collected at registration may include:

- Race
- Ethnicity
- Gender Identity
- State of Residency
- Urban/Rurality
- Affiliation with RADx-UP (community partner, academic researcher, staff, NIH leadership, etc.)

(B) PROCESS AND OUTCOME DATA COLLECTION

EA events have included evaluations at the end of breakout presentations, roundtable discussions, and at the conclusion of the event. Process and outcome data have been collected for process improvement purposes and to measure the impact of the EA event on attendees' project work.

- **EA Event Survey Descriptions**
 - **Breakout Session Surveys** include questions to determine if the presentations' objectives are met, which are provided by presenters before the event. Attendees are also asked to rate the quality of the session and to share what they liked or what could be improved in the future. Time should be provided during the last 3 – 5 minutes of the session for attendees to fill out the survey, which is provided in the session chat. Session facilitators are responsible for prompting attendees to participate in the evaluation.
 - **Roundtable Discussion Surveys** ask attendees to rate the quality of the session and to share what they liked about the session and what could be improved in the session. In past events the survey has included questions designed to determine if attendees engaged in networking during the roundtable. The survey is disseminated and prompted to attendees via the session chat by the facilitator during the last 3 – 5 minutes of the session.
 - **Overall Event Evaluation Surveys** are announced by EA Leadership and disseminated at the closing event session on Day 2 in the session chat. They are also immediately sent via email to all attendees once the event has ended. This survey has included questions that evaluate attendees' perceived quality of the event, whether participants learned applicable information, the likelihood that attendees will use the information in their work, and whether they engaged in meaningful networking.
 - **Post Event Evaluation Surveys** are distributed two-months following the event, and survey questions have included whether participants have applied information learned at the event to their work, if they intend to apply information, and what barriers may exist for doing so.
- **Qualitative Data Collection:** To learn more about attendees' experiences with the EA event, EA Data Profile, and post-event dissemination qualitative interviews have been conducted using an interview guide co-developed by the evaluation and IOT teams.

(A) VOLUNTEER RECRUITMENT AND TRAINING

The number of volunteers and the needed volunteer roles is determined by the upcoming event's agenda and the number of participants expected at the event. EA volunteer roles are listed below with the processes for recruitment and training. Typically, each breakout presentation and each roundtable room will need one facilitator and one notetaker. Each theme should be assigned an individual reporter who will attend their assigned theme's breakout presentation session(s) and will float between its roundtable discussions. Descriptions of volunteer roles can be found in Appendix E.

- **Virtual Chat Monitors and Session Notetakers: Recruitment and Training**

Steps to recruit, train and manage the chat monitor and notetaker roles are detailed below. These roles do not require public speaking or facilitation skills but should be performed by individuals who are digital natives or comfortable with learning new virtual skills. Each breakout presentation should have one chat monitor and one notetaker, and each roundtable room should have at least one notetaker. The chat monitor can also hold another role during the session such as facilitator or notetaker.

 - Identify how many volunteers are needed based on the number of themes and the number of simultaneous sessions planned for each day.
 - Draft descriptions for each volunteer role so you can provide enough information to help the volunteer determine if they can perform the role. See Appendix E for volunteer roles.
 - Recruiting Volunteers (Chat Monitor and Notetakers only): Draft a call for volunteers to be sent to staff. Communicate roles, expectations, and training requirements to perform the role. Include a digital volunteer sign-up form that captures data needed for coordination of training, assigning roles, and contacting volunteers.
 - Send the recruitment email to individuals who volunteered in previous EAs first and provide a deadline to commit. Once the deadline has passed, assess how many volunteers are still needed and further disseminate the recruitment message across to other staff members.
 - Once most volunteer needs for the chat monitor and notetaker roles are filled send out calendar holds and session assignments to each volunteer and announce times and dates for training.
 - Disseminate a volunteer guide and access to any needed resources such as notetaking templates or links to sessions specific to the role prior to the event and include instructions for how to access the volunteer 'hub' (see section B below) and a communications plan for the day of the event.

- **Facilitator Recruitment, Training and Management**
 - Identify previous EA volunteers or other staff members with experience in public speaking and facilitating discussions and invite these targeted individuals. Provide role descriptions, role expectations, and other needed details.
 - Send out individual invites to volunteers with a deadline for commitment. Once the deadline has passed, assess if any additional volunteers are needed.
 - Disseminate a facilitation guide that includes a script that informs the volunteer when to provide instructions such as when attendees should fill out session surveys.
 - Breakout Presentation facilitators should be provided with a short script to introduce their assigned session's speaker(s) and a few questions to ask during the Q&A if attendees have not submitted questions.
 - Coordinate a training session(s) that includes time for both virtual platform navigation training and time for facilitation guidance review.
 - Provide access to any needed resources such as notetaking templates or links to sessions specific to the role prior to the event and include instructions for how to access the volunteer 'hub' (see section B below) and a communications plan for the day of the event.

(B) VOLUNTEER RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT AND DISSEMINATION

- **Volunteer Guide:** Volunteers will receive a guide prior to the event which will also be presented during volunteer training. Each of the volunteer roles should have a separate guide with instructions and links to needed resources to perform the role. Include timing for when certain roles should transition between sessions, close sessions, share surveys, etc. Supplemental training materials may include videos demonstrating how to navigate the virtual platform or screenshots provided in a document.
- **Volunteer 'Hub':** Volunteer guides, supplemental training materials, relevant session links, and relevant document links should be stored in an online shared folder/space for volunteers to easily access the materials as needed before and during the event. The IOT team should be ready to provide a link to this central 'hub' during the event in case a volunteer needs quick access. A link and/or instructions to find the 'hub' should be simple and clearly defined in communications with volunteers preceding the event.
- **Communications Plan:** A centralized group chat using WhatsApp, Slack, or another communications tool that all volunteers have access to, should be set up for day of communications, and a team member should be assigned to monitor it before and during the event so they can easily assist volunteers as needed. It is also helpful for all volunteers assigned to the same theme to establish a direct line of communication with one another so they can keep one another informed as needed.

ARTICLE 3. POST EVENT ACTIVITIES

THE PURPOSE OF THE EA SUMMARY REPORT IS TO FURTHER DISSEMINATE THE KEY TAKEAWAYS AND LESSONS LEARNED THAT ARE IDENTIFIED AT AN EA EVENT BY SUMMARIZING THE EVENT'S PRESENTATIONS, ROUNDTABLE DISCUSSIONS, AND KEYNOTE ADDRESSES AND BY PROVIDING AN EXECUTIVE SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION OF COMPREHENSIVE LESSONS LEARNED.

(A) EA SUMMARY REPORT

The EA Summary Report is published within 2 months of the EA event and disseminated to attendees and other RADx-UP stakeholders. It should include the following sections: an executive summary, demographic infographics, purpose of the EA, thematic summaries that include takeaways from themes' breakout and roundtable sessions, and a conclusion of lessons learned.

- **Compiling and Documenting EA Event's Key Takeaways and Lessons Learned**
 - Following the EA event's close, IOT members should thematically compile and save all sessions' notes taken by notetakers, presenters' slide decks, recordings of the presentations, and sessions' chat transcripts.
 - Recorded presentations and slide decks should be published on the RADx-UP EA webpage.
 - Each theme's compiled resources should be reviewed and a thematic bulleted summary of the key takeaways from breakout presentations and the lessons learned from the roundtable sessions should be drafted and cross checked by other team members. Summaries should include links to session recordings and slide decks for readers to learn more.
 - Keynote addresses should be summarized in a short narrative form.
 - Leadership members are to draft an executive summary that introduces the event's themes, goals, objectives, an attendee demographic profile (infographics recommended), and a conclusion that summarizes the comprehensive lessons learned throughout the event.
 - Leadership should provide the executive summary and lessons learned section to bookend the keynote and theme summaries.
 - The Summary Report will be translated to Spanish and go through a graphic design process.
- **EA Summary Report Dissemination:**
 - The Summary Report will be posted on the EA website in both English and Spanish and featured as a 'news' article on the RADx-UP website.

- The report should also be disseminated via email to the entire RADx-UP enterprise, attendees, and other stakeholders. The email message should include a high-level description of the content provided in the Summary Report and details for how to access event content online.

(B) COMMUNITY DISSEMINATION

Purpose: To support dissemination and adoption of the key takeaways and lessons learned at the EA event to community partners and lay audience stakeholders.

After the EA event the IOT should determine the best format to disseminate the key takeaways and lessons learned based on current resources, trends in engagement, and successes and challenges of past efforts. Past examples include turnkey slide decks, webpages, webinars, and speaker spotlight articles published online. Once a format has been determined and resources are developed, the content should be reviewed by community partners in English and Spanish and then revised to reflect their feedback. The final versions of resources should be published on the RADx-UP website and disseminated via the listserv, social media, the attendee list, and to other stakeholders via email.

- **Documenting Lessons Learned:** Shortly after the EA event the IOT should document or hold a debriefing meeting to determine what aspects of the event planning and execution worked well and opportunities for improvement for future events. Lessons learned and processes should be documented and saved in an easily accessible folder so that the team can reference past processes and documents that can be duplicated or adapted for the next event cycle.

Once all evaluation activities of the EA are complete, the evaluation team will provide a slide deck of the evaluation results including an analysis of surveys, qualitative interviews, and recommendations.